

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357992599>

THE IMPACT OF STRESS IN TRAINEES UNDER THE EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE: A STUDY MULTICULTURAL BETWEEN PORTUGAL AND BRAZIL

Conference Paper · January 2011

CITATIONS

0

READS

29

7 authors, including:

Leandra Fernandes Procopio

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid

27 PUBLICATIONS 9 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Anabela Pereira

University of Aveiro

336 PUBLICATIONS 2,626 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Marcos Procopio

Universidad Castilla la Mancha, España, Toledo

20 PUBLICATIONS 19 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Dulceria Tartuci

Universidade Federal de Catalão, Brasil, Catalão

24 PUBLICATIONS 32 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

THE IMPACT OF STRESS IN TRAINEES UNDER THE EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE: A STUDY MULTICULTURAL BETWEEN PORTUGAL AND BRAZIL

Leandra Fernandes¹; Anabela Pereira¹; Luísa Santos¹; Carlos Francisco²; Elianda Tiballi³; Marcos Procópio³

¹ Universidade de Aveiro: leandrafernandes@ua.pt; anabelapereira@ua.pt; luisa.santos@ua.pt

² Escola Superior de Educação da Guarda: cmfrancisco@sapo.pt

³ Pontifícia Universidade Católica de Goiás – PUC-Goiás: tiballi@terra.com.br; quanticis@gmail.com;

ABSTRACT

This multicultural and international research aims at identifying the major sources of stress in inducing trainees during the probationary period of teaching practice as well as the occurrence of these characteristics teachers among future. This study, a quantitative and comparative nature, has a sample of 476 Portuguese trainees (M = 49 and F = 427) and 490 Brazilians (M = 113 and F = 377) of initial teacher education institutions, 8 Higher central Portugal and Brazil. Was used as an instrument in the questionnaire "stress evaluation of the student intern" (Francisco & Pereira, 2003), whose results show that in both countries the teaching practice is appointed by the trainees as significantly inducing stress, and Portuguese women the most affected. In Brazil, the levels of stress are felt most at the end of the probationary period for both sexes, while for the top trainees Portuguese is more stressful. Implication of this study and as a continuum, further comparative studies are currently under development in institutions of higher education in Portugal and Brazil.

INTRODUCTION

The health and well being of students, especially in higher education, is a matter of high concern among many researchers (Dunham, 1992; Jesus, 2002; Francisco & Pereira, 2006), particularly with respect to the stressful nature of this phase. The changes, in the cognitive, social and academic areas, as well as the nature of the preparation of their future profession exercise and the organization of this work, particularly in the context of probation, may contribute to the development of emotional disorders.

Some authors (Almeida, 1997; Caire, 2001; Capel e col., 1997; Francisco, Pereira, 2004, 2005) indicate that levels of stress experienced by academics in the probationary period very depending on the level of risk / threat perceived by the subject and that each student intern has different and unique reactions when facing very similar situations. The number of studies (Alarcão & Tavares, 2003; Caires, 2003; Cordeiro, 1997; Cardoso, 1999; Francisco & Pereira, 2003; Flores 2000) about becoming a teacher is increasing since there is a consensus about the fact that teaching practice is one of the most remarkable periods of initial training for future teachers. In this sense, we find in literature a variety of factors that induce stress, such as institutional, interpersonal and intrapersonal stressors, along with training and professional factors (Francisco, 2006, 110).

Having in consideration all these factors to which the trainee is exposed, it is natural that the physical symptoms (changes in sleep, appetite, tremors, pain and stress states,...), the behavioral symptoms (voluntary withdrawal or not, mood changes, increased consumption of substance) and cognitive symptoms (low morale, concentration and self-confidence, depression, anxiety and crying) appear and compromise performance at both academic and cognitive level and in relationships. Exposure to as many factors as sources of stress, can lead to a poor performance, to higher levels of anxiety, depression, and may trigger the onset of diseases related to physical and mental health (Dunham, 1992; Jesus, 2002).

Taking into account all this complexity involved in the period of training in teacher education, we decided to make a comparative study between Portugal and Brazil, whose goal is to identify the main sources of stress in inducing trainees during the probationary period of teaching practice and to know the characteristics this occurrence among future teachers, given that the attention to these future health professionals may have consequences in the well-being of the population they attend.

METHODOLOGY

Sample

The sample consists of 966 trainees, 476 (49,3%) of which are portuguese students (M = 49 e F = 427) and 490 (50,7 %) Brazilian (M= 113 e F = 377). In what concerns to gender, 83,2 % were female and 16.8 % male. The age varied between 19 and 49 years in Portugal, with an average of 23.75 years and from 18 to 57 years in Brazil, with the average for 27.25 years. Regarding marital status, the majority in both countries was single (N = 413 in Portugal and N = 310 in Brazil). In Brazil 17.81% (n = 172) of the subjects have children, while in Portugal this percentage is 4.06% (N = 39).

In Portugal we have graduates from the University of Aveiro (19.8 %), the School of Education (ESES) of the cities of Viseu (11,3 %), Leiria (11,5 %) and Coimbra (6,7 %). In Brazil, data was collected in four institutions of higher education in the city of Goiania, being the UFG - Federal University of Goiás (14,8%), PUC-Goiás - Católica Pontifical University of Goiás (15.4%), the School Standard (14.3%) and the Faculty Araguaia (6.2%). Of these, three are universities and five are polytechnics (ESE / Colleges).

Teacher education programs covered in this study were divided into two groups. Group 1 consists of the professional degrees for early childhood education and elementary education 1st. and 2nd cycles (elementary school I) and group 2 consists of the degrees that allow clearance for the 3. nd cycle of basic education (junior II) and secondary (high school). In the first group, there were Pedagogy courses (29.4%), Early Childhood Education (24.7%), Teacher of Basic Education (14.5%) and a Bachelor of Physical Education (8.6 %), with a total of 77.2% of subjects. In group 2, there are the degrees in Physical Chemistry (2.2%), Biology / Geology (5.1%), Mathematics (4.5%), Music (4.3%), Humanities (2.5%), Geography (3.1%) and History (1.1%), constituting 22.8% of the total sample.

Instrument

The protocol applied consisted of questions to collect sociodemographic and academic data, as well as questions about perceived stress levels and a questionnaire about "Sources of stress in the student intern" of Francisco et al. (2006). The 30 items of this instrument correspond to five factors that induce stress ("Insecurity in the face of Performance", "Problems of indiscipline"; "Supervision"; "Work Overload and Interpersonal Relations"), and are responded in a five points Likert scale (from Very Dissatisfied to Very Satisfied).

The coefficient of internal consistency of the dimensions ranged from $\alpha = .68$ to $\alpha = .93$, and for the total scale was obtained a coefficient $\alpha = .91$, which can be considered quite appropriate, being in line with the value $\alpha = .92$ presented by the authors of the questionnaire (Francisco et al., 2006).

Procedure

Data collection was performed during the year 2008/2009, through the granting of permits by the eight higher education institutions involved and with the support of the coordinators of their teaching practice and internship supervisors. Anonymity and confidentiality of data were maintained. The data were inserted in SPSS - Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) version 18.0 for Windows.

Results and discussion

In what concerns to the stress felt by the trainees during the probationary period of teaching practice, we found that 6,3% assess this stage as a period of low stress, 56.3% as moderate and 37.4% as high stress. In Brazil, 17.8% of trainees assess this stage as a period of low stress, 49.2% as moderate and 33.1% as high stress, demonstrating that in Portugal the rate of moderate and high stress are higher than in Brazil.

Regarding the periods of the school year in which stress is felt most by scholars, we observe that in Portugal the beginning is considered by the majority (75.7%) in both sexes, as the most stressful period. In Brazil, the data were inverse, indicating that for 75.3%, the end of the probationary period is the most stressful time.

When comparing data by country, significant differences were found between Portugal and Brazil. More specifically, there were differences in the "Insecurity in the face of professional performance", "Supervision" and "Overload of work". In all of these factors, the averages were higher in the Portuguese group (see Table 1). These data corroborate to previous studies (Francisco & Pereira, 2002, 2004, Francisco et al., 2005).

Table 1. Comparison in means stress factors between Portugal and Brazil

Stress Factors	Portugal		Brazil		t-test	p
	Means	DP	Means	DP		
1 Insecurity in the face of professional performance	30,8	6,2	27,86	6,9	7,10	,000
2 Problems of indiscipline	25,9	5,6	25,4	6,2	1,42	,156
3 Supervision	17,1	3,9	15,6	4,2	5,85	,000
4 Overload of work	18,8	3,4	17,4	3,8	5,81	,000
5 Interpersonal Relations	9,36	2,7	9,92	2,8	- 3,15	,002

When established an analysis taking into account the student workers, we found significantly higher mean stress on academics who are not employed (see Table 2).

Table 2: Comparison of means between student workers and non workers

Student Workers	Means	DP	Test-t	p
1 Yes (N= 404)	2,17	0,78	-2,28	0,023
2 No (N= 562)	2,27	0,60		

In the analysis of the factors that induce stress taking into account the sex variable, we found that women had higher average levels in "Work overload", "Supervision", and "Insecurity and professional". Portuguese women were the most affected mainly in the variables "work overload", "Supervision" and "Problems of indiscipline". In Brazil, women have on average higher values only for the factor "supervision".

A comparison of gender in the total sample shows that there are significant differences in the factors "Insecurity in the face of professional performance", "Supervision" and "Work Overload", belonging the highest average to women in all these factors. (see Table 3) These results confirm previous studies, which indicate that those women with higher symptoms of stress; (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Jesus et al., 1992; Francisco, 2003).

Table 3: Comparison of means by gender for the total sample

Stress Factors		Male		Female		t-test	P
		Means	DP	Means	DP		
1	Insecurity in the face of professional performance	26.77	6.67	29.85	6.60	- 5.40	0.000
2	Problems of indiscipline	24.81	6.45	25.86	5.79	- 1.92	0.06
3	Supervision	14.55	4.17	16.70	4.06	- 6.11	0.000
4	Overload of work	17.02	3.88	18.31	3.62	- 4.09	0.000
5	Interpersonal Relations	9.46	2.934	9.68	2.74	- 0.90	0.37

CONCLUSION

Given that the route of an investigation is always incomplete, since the knowledge does not become scarce when exploited, we can conclude based on a review of the literature and extensive field research, that the stage is configured as a source of stress and that the main stressors are “Insecurity in the face of professional performance”, “Supervision” and “Work Overload”. We can conclude that women are most affected by stress and when considering the country, Portugal presented the highest rates of stress.

We can infer from these results that the concern with the development of individual capacities to control and manage stress, should also occur during the initial formation of academic and should focus especially during the period of teaching practice. It is also important to promote a greater monitoring / support of the student intern, through study groups, help lines, personal and social development sessions, essential to resilience, satisfaction with social support, thus increasing the safety, well-being and individual capacity to mobilize internal and external resources to help avoiding stress.

Once the trainee students, especially the training of teachers involved in the period of teaching practice move in complex systems, consisting of a wide diversity of elements linked by strong interact, such as school, parents, students, discipline, paperwork, appraisals, and others, we believe it is important to invest in education, training and welfare of the student intern, so that we can not only increase their academic performance, but also so that this welfare is transmitted in the classroom, to their future students.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alarcão, I. & Tavares, J. (2003). *Supervisão da prática pedagógica: Uma perspectiva de desenvolvimento e aprendizagem*. (2nd ed.). Coimbra: Livraria Almedina.
- Caires, S. (2003). *Vivências e percepções do estágio pedagógico: A perspectiva dos estagiários da Universidade do Minho*. Tese de Doutoramento em Psicologia, na especialidade de Psicologia da Educação. Braga: Universidade do Minho.
- Capel, S., & Blair, R. (2007). Making physical education relevant: Increasing the impact of initial teacher education, *London Review of Education*, 5 (1), 15-34.

- Capel, S., Zwozdiak-Myers, P., & Lawrence, J. (2007). The transfer of pupils from primary to secondary school: A case study of a foundation subject - physical education, *Research in Education*, 77, 14-30.
- Cordeiro A., F. (1997). A (In)satisfação dos Professores. In M. T. Estrela (Org.), *Viver e Construir a Profissão Docente* (pp. 81-116). Porto Editora.
- Dunham, J. (1992). *Stress in Teaching*. London. Routledge.
- Francisco, C. M., & Pereira, A.M.S. (2004). Desenvolvimento Pessoal: Profissionalidade e docência no ano de estágio. *Docência e aprendizagem no ensino superior – d@es*. http://webct2.ua.pt/public/leies/daes_artigos.htm. Disponível em 1 de Junho de 2004.
- Francisco, C., Pereira, A.M.S., & Pereira, G. (2004). Fontes de stresse do estudante estagiário: Contributos da supervisão para o bem-estar do aluno. In Ribeiro, J. & Leal, I. (Eds.), *Actas do 5 Congresso de Psicologia da Saúde* (pp. 111-117). Lisboa: Fundação Calouste, ISPA edições.
- Francisco, C., Pereira, A.M.S., & Pereira, M.G. (2005). Como vai a saúde dos alunos estagiários? Avaliar para intervir. In *Actas VIII Congresso Galaico Português PsicoPedagogia* (pp.1043-1050. Setembro, Universidade do Minho..
- Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P. & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (2004). *Supervision of instruction: A developmental approach*. (5th ed.). Massachusetts: Allyn & Bacon.
- Haritos, C. (2004). Understanding teaching through the minds of teacher candidates: a curious blend of realism and idealism. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20, 637-654.
- Jesus, S. N., Abreu, M. V., Santos, E. R., & Pereira, A. M. (1992). Estudo dos factores de mal-estar na profissão docente. *Psychologica*, 8, 51-60.
- Jesus, S. N. (1996). *A Motivação para a Profissão Docente*. Col. Ciências da Educação e Desenvolvimento Humano. Estante Editora.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, Appraisal and Coping*. New York: Springer Publishing Company.
- Mota-Cardoso, R., Araújo, A., Ramos, R.C., Gonçalves, G. & Ramos, M. (2002). *O Stress nos Professores Portugueses – Estudo IPSSO 2000*. Porto: Porto Editora.
- Pereira, A.M.S. (1999). Sucesso versus Insucesso: Taxonomia das necessidades do aluno. In José Tavares (Eds.), *IV Congresso da Sociedade Portuguesa de Ciências da Educação* (pp.129-136). Investigar e Formar em Educação, Vol I, Aveiro.